

Beyond Source Code: Evaluating Behavioral Specifications for LLM-Based C-to-Rust Translation [Supplementary Data]

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I. PROMPTS USED FOR GENERATING UNVALIDATED SPECIFICATIONS

```
You are an expert senior software engineer.
Given source code, generate a precise, structured
behavioral specification that states WHAT the code
guarantees, not HOW it achieves it.
Output must use exactly these sections and headings:
1. Functional Description
2. Inputs
2. Outputs
4. Preconditions
5. Postconditions
6. Invariants
7. Error Handling / Exceptional Behavior
8. State Transitions (if applicable)
9. Non-functional Constraints (if inferable)
Content requirements:
- Be concise and contract-focused; omit incidental or
low-level details.
- Do not reference language/library APIs, format strings,
or identifiers (e.g., no mentions of scanf, printf,
fgets, variable or function names, loop types, or
recursion).
- Describe I/O abstractly (e.g., "reads values from
standard input" or "returns a value"); never cite exact
parsing patterns or format specifiers.
- Do not restate implementation structure or control
flow. Focus on observable behavior, data constraints, and
guarantees.
- If behavior is ambiguous, state explicit assumptions.
If something cannot be deduced, write "Not inferable from
code."
- Avoid extreme assumptions. Capture only behavior
implied by the code's observable contract.
- If the program is an executable, treat printing/writing
as side effects in Outputs.
- No code, no pseudocode, no preamble or epilogue text.
Use only the nine sections above.
- Return only the nine sections with the exact headings
and numbering specified. Do not include any other text,
examples, or code.
Now generate the specification for the code below:
<code>
```

Listing 1: Prompt template used for specification generation

II. PROMPT TEMPLATES USED FOR GENERATING VALIDATED SPECIFICATIONS

```
You are a senior systems engineer fluent in C, with
strong expertise in program semantics and systems
programming.
Task:
Translate the given Specification into C code.
Primary goal:
Preserve semantics based ONLY on the Specification
provided. Do not assume any external code or source.
Instructions:
1) Treat the Specification as the only source of truth
for behavior.
2) Preserve observable I/O behavior described in the
Specification.
3) Preserve corner-case behavior implied by the
Specification. For example, if the Specification relies
on:
- integer overflow / wraparound,
- bit-level tricks,
- undefined/implementation-defined behavior,
then emulate the intended behavior as closely as possible
in C.
4) If the Specification is incomplete, ambiguous, or
inconsistent:
- do not invent extra functionality
- choose the narrowest reasonable interpretation
justified by the Specification
- produce compilable C code that stays as faithful as
possible to the stated behavior
5) You may add comments as needed to explain non-obvious
translation choices, especially if they relate to
preserving semantics or handling corner cases.
6) Any explanation must appear only as valid C comments
inside the code and not after the code.
7) Return ONLY the C code in a single ``c code block.
Specification:
``text
spec
``
```

Listing 2: Prompt template used for Back Translation of Specification back to C code to validate specification correctness

```

Diagnosis generation
You are analyzing a natural-language specification
against a source program.
You are given:
1. The source program
2. The current specification derived from the source
3. A failing test case showing that code generated from
the specification does not match the source behavior
Your task is NOT to repair the specification yet.
Your task is to infer what this failure suggests about
the specification.
Important rules:
- Treat the source program as the only ground truth.
- Treat the failing test only as evidence of possible
mismatch.
- Do NOT suggest patching the specification to satisfy
this one test case.
- Infer only general issues supported by the source
program.
- Do NOT restate the test as a special-case rule.
Please analyze:
- what part of the source behavior is likely missing,
vague, or incorrect in the current specification
- whether the failure suggests a missing edge case,
missing constraint, wrong abstraction, wrong transition
rule, wrong counting rule, wrong termination condition,
wrong ordering rule, or wrong assumption
Output format:
A. Likely mismatch category
B. What the current specification may be missing or
misstating
C. What general behavior should be clarified in the
specification
D. Why this clarification is supported by the source
program
Source program:
``c
<original_code>
``
Current specification:
``text
<current_spec>
``
Generated C program from the current specification:
``c
<generated_code>
``
Failing execution report:
``text
<report_text>
``

```

Listing 3: Prompt template used for diagnosing missing information during specification validation

```

Fix spec
You are revising a natural-language specification for a
program.
You are given:
1. The source program
2. The current specification
3. An analysis of likely mismatches between the source
and the current specification
Your task:
Revise the specification so that it more faithfully
captures the source program.
Important rules:
- The source program is the only ground truth.
- Preserve correct parts of the current specification.
- Revise only parts that are incomplete, ambiguous,
over-abstracted, or incorrect.
- Do NOT optimize for any specific failing test.
- Do NOT mention specific test inputs, outputs, or
examples in the revised specification.
- Add only behavior justified by the source program.
- Prefer general semantic clarification over ad hoc
patching.
- Do not be too specific about implementation details.
Focus especially on clarifying:
- input assumptions and constraints
- edge cases
- state transitions
- counting logic
- ordering/tie-breaking
- termination behavior
- output semantics
Output format:
Just provide the revised specification
Source program:
``c
original_code
``
Current specification:
``text
current_spec
``
Mismatch analysis:
``text
diagnosi_text
``

```

Listing 4: Prompt template used for updating specification using LLM diagnosis information

III. PROMPTS USED FOR TRANSLATION TO RUST

```
You are a senior systems engineer fluent in C and Rust,
with strong expertise in program semantics and safe
systems programming.
Task:
Translate the given Specification into Rust code.
Primary goal:
Preserve semantics based ONLY on the Specification
provided. Do not assume any external code or source.
Instructions:
1) Treat the Specification as the only source of truth
for behavior.
2) Preserve observable I/O behavior described in the
Specification.
3) Preserve corner-case behavior implied by the
Specification. For example, if the Specification relies
on:
- integer overflow / wraparound,
- bit-level tricks,
- undefined/implementation-defined behavior,
then emulate the intended behavior as closely as possible
in Rust.
4) If the Specification is incomplete, ambiguous, or
inconsistent:
- do not invent extra functionality
- choose the narrowest reasonable interpretation
justified by the Specification
- produce compilable Rust that stays as faithful as
possible to the stated behavior
5) Prefer safe, idiomatic Rust:
- Avoid `unsafe` unless necessary; if used, justify it in
a short comment.
6) You may add comments as needed to explain non-obvious
translation choices, especially if they relate to
preserving semantics or handling corner cases.
7) Any explanation must appear only as valid Rust
comments inside the code and not after the code.
8) Return ONLY the Rust code in a single ``rust code
block.
``text
Specification
``
```

Listing 5: Prompt Template Used For Generating Rust Code From Specification Only

```
You are a senior systems engineer fluent in C and Rust,
with strong expertise in program semantics and safe
systems programming.
Task:
Translate the given C code into Rust.
Primary goal:
Preserve semantics based ONLY on the C code provided. Do
not assume any external specification.
Instructions:
1) Treat the C code as the only source of truth for
behavior.
2) Preserve I/O behavior exactly (stdin/stdout
formatting, whitespace, newlines).
3) Preserve corner-case behavior implied by the C code.
For example, if the C code relies on:
- integer overflow / wraparound,
- bit-level tricks,
- undefined/implementation-defined behavior,
then emulate the intended behavior as closely as possible
in Rust.
4) Prefer safe, idiomatic Rust:
- Avoid `unsafe` unless necessary; if used, justify it in
a short comment.
5) You may add comments as needed to explain non-obvious
translation choices, especially if they relate to
preserving semantics or handling corner cases or just
as a human developer would to clarify intent.
6) Return ONLY the Rust code in a single ``rust code
block.
Now translate the following.
``
<code>
``
```

Listing 6: Prompt Template Used For Generating Rust Code From C Code Only

```

You are a senior systems engineer fluent in C and
Rust, with strong expertise in program semantics and
specification-driven translation.
Task:
Translate the given C code into Rust, using the provided
code and specification as the source-of-truth for
intended behavior.
Primary goal:
Preserve semantics. The Rust code must satisfy the
specification (functional behavior, preconditions,
postconditions, invariants, and error behavior).
Instructions:
1) Read the SPEC first and treat it as the definitive
description of expected behavior.
2) Use the C code only to resolve ambiguities and edge
cases and do not implement any non implemented function.
3) If the C code conflicts with the spec, follow the spec
and explicitly note the mismatch.
4) Prefer safe, idiomatic Rust:
- Strongly Avoid `unsafe` unless necessary; if used,
justify it in a short comment. Prioritise converting
unsafe code to safe code.
5) Preserve I/O behavior exactly (stdin/stdout
formatting, whitespace, newlines).
6) Avoid unsafe unless absolutely necessary.
7) You may add comments as needed to explain non-obvious
translation choices, especially if they relate to
preserving semantics or handling corner cases or just
as a human developer would to clarify intent.
8) Return ONLY the Rust code in a single ``rust code
block.
Now translate the following code using the specification.
=== SPECIFICATION START ===
specification text
=== SPECIFICATION END ===
=== C CODE START ===
<code>
=== C CODE END ==="

```

Listing 7: Prompt Template Used For Generating Rust Code Using Both Code and Specification

```

The previous repair attempt was executed and did not
fully pass.
Attempt number: attempt_number
Observed status: status
Latest execution report:
``text
report_text
``
Latest Rust code:
``rust
code_text
``
Please produce an improved repaired Rust file. Return
only the Rust code in a single ``rust code block.

```

Listing 8: Prompt Template Used For Generating Updated Rust Code At Attempts 2 and 3 Given the Rust Code Execution Report